

Force Measurements to Advance the Design and Implantation of CMOS-Based Neural Probes

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Abstract—Objective: Tissue penetrating active neural probes provide large and densely packed microelectrode arrays for the fine-grained investigation of brain circuits and for advancing brain-machine interfaces (BMIs). To improve the electrical interfacing performances of such stiff silicon devices, which typically elicit a vigorous foreign body reaction (FBR), here we perform insertion force measurements and derive probe layout and implantation procedure optimizations. **Methods:** We performed in-vivo insertion force measurements to evaluate the impact of probe design and implantation speed on mechanically induced trauma and iatrogenic injury. Because acute damage constitutes the initial trigger of FBR, these experiments allow to characterize and minimize device invasiveness. **Results:** Probe sharpness outweighs cross-sectional dimensions during the dimpling stage of the implantation, when the device compresses the brain before penetration. Insertion speed does not display a major effect on dimpling magnitude. A slow speed, however, significantly increases dimpling duration. **Conclusion:** It is crucial to use sharp devices to reduce mechanical and ischemic damage. Although slow insertion speeds typically improve the quality of acute electrophysiological recordings, we show that slow speeds should only be used upon penetration in the brain parenchyma and not during the dimpling stage. A closed-loop implantation procedure can be used to set the appropriate speed in the different insertion stages. **Significance:** We provide new evidence on the impact of probe layout and insertion speed on insertion force, with implications on the design and implantation procedure for minimally invasive CMOS neural probes. A novel closed-loop

methodology to optimize device implantation and reduce FBR is proposed.

Index Terms—Acute tissue damage, brain-machine interfaces, buckling, dimpling force, intracortical neural probes.

I. INTRODUCTION

ACTIVE tissue penetrating neural probes realized with Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (CMOS) technology can provide a drastically higher electrode density and array size compared to conventional microstructured passive electrode array devices [1], [2], [3]. This approach introduces novel opportunities both for neuroscientific research and for the development of BMIs based on large data bandwidth interfaces [4]. However, CMOS technology imposes the use of a stiff silicon substrate, which is typically associated with a more vigorous FBR compared to flexible polymeric materials [5], [6]. FBR is the cascade of biological responses elicited when a foreign body, in this case a neural probe, is introduced inside the brain. This biological response constitutes a strong hindrance to chronic neural interfacing applications due to the progressive decrease in signal quality that it entails [7], [8]. One potential strategy to exploit the superior electrode density of active CMOS probes while mitigating the drawbacks associated with a stiff substrate is to minimize the iatrogenic injury that is induced during implantation. Indeed, it is widely recognized that this initial neurovascular and cortical damage constitutes a critical trigger for the subsequent activation of FBR [9]. To this end, the study of axial insertion force emerges as an interesting metric to evaluate the initial implantation damage and to guide optimizations towards the minimization of invasiveness. For instance, McNamara et al. [10] highlight the lack of force measurements as a limitation of their study on the tissue damage caused by tissue-penetrating microwire arrays.

Multiple studies have demonstrated the impact of parameters such as probe size [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], tip geometry [11], [15], [16], speed [11], [12], [13], [16], [17], [18], and surface properties [19], [20] on the axial insertion force measured in-vivo. Insertion force relates both device features and implantation procedure with the extent of mechanical trauma and tissue disruption induced by device insertion. Based on the reported evidence, probe implantation can generally be divided into two main stages:

Received 31 July 2024; revised 18 November 2024; accepted 16 December 2024. Date of publication 18 December 2024; date of current version 23 April 2025. This work was supported in part by the European Union – NextGenerationEU through the Project “RAISE - Robotics and AI for Socio-economic Empowerment” and in part by European Innovation Council (Horizon-EIC) through the Crossbrain project under Grant 101070908. (Luca Berdondini and Joao F. Ribeiro are last authors.) (Corresponding author: Alberto Perna.)

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This article has supplementary downloadable material available at <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2024.3519763>, provided by the authors.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TBME.2024.3519763

- the dimpling stage, during which the probe compresses elastically the surface of the brain. The force required for brain penetration is referred to as the dimpling force.
- further insertion of the device within the brain parenchyma.

Probe cross-sectional dimensions [11], [14], [15], [16], [20], [21] and tip geometry [11], [15], [16], [22], [21] are reported to play an important role during the dimpling stage of the implantation, where smaller and sharper probes typically reduce overall tissue compression. The presence of the dura mater membrane significantly affects this implantation stage. Indeed, insertion through the stiff dura [14], [16], [22] requires much larger dimpling forces as opposed to experimental conditions where a durotomy is performed beforehand [11], [15], [20], [23]. After the dimpling stage, probes with larger cross-sectional dimensions generally require a higher force for further insertion inside the brain parenchyma [11], [13], [16], [20]. This is because these probes displace a larger volume of tissue as they are inserted and give rise to a larger contact area with the brain parenchyma. The surface properties of implantable probes have also been shown to influence this stage of implantation. Sridharan et al. [19] reported that probes with a more compliant surface (lower Young's modulus) induced significantly less strain compared to silicon probes. Other studies showed that surface modifications both with hydrophilic [20], [24] and hydrophobic coatings [20] reduces insertion force.

A few studies have so far investigated the impact of insertion speed on implantation dynamics. In most cases, a lower speed was observed to reduce dimpling forces and tissue compression [14], [16], [25], [26]. Conversely, one study reported the opposite observation [13] and two other studies have shown no appreciable effects of insertion speed on the dimpling force [11], [17]. This discrepancy may be explained by the different speeds (from 2 $\mu\text{m/s}$ to 1.67 mm/s), types of devices (e.g., microwires, silicon probes, etc.) and experimental conditions (with or without removal of the dura) used in these works. After the dimpling stage, slower speeds are generally reported to reduce overall insertion force [12], [18], [21].

In the literature, some research effort has also been devoted to simulate through computational models the impact of device size [27], [28] and insertion procedure [28] on the acute tissue trauma generated by implantation. This approach has the advantage of greatly increasing the number and combination of conditions that can be tested in a short time. However, extensive experimental validation is typically required to corroborate the outcomes of simulations [29].

Here, we present new experimental evidence concerning the impact of device size and tip geometry on the dimpling stage of the insertion. These results complement the preliminary data that we reported previously [15] and considerably expand its significance. Differently from other studies, which focused on characterizing the implantation dynamics of microwires and passive neural probes, we used silicon devices with the typical geometries and cross-sectional dimensions of active CMOS-based probes. The active electronic circuitry within CMOS probes enables to multiplex multiple electrode signals into a single output line. This advancement allows to use a constant cross-section and to reduce shank width while maintaining a

Fig. 1. SEM image of a neural probes used in this study indicating the key dimensional features: α tip angle, β tip angle, probe width (W) and probe thickness (H). Representative SEM images of all the silicon probes used in this work are reported in Supplementary Fig. 2.

TABLE I
SUMMARY TABLE OF PROBE GEOMETRICAL FEATURES

Probe code	α tip angle	β tip angle	W [μm]	H [μm]
Type A	40°	85°	32	50
Type B	40°	85°	86	50
Type C	20°	85°	38	15
Type D	20°	85°	86	50
Type E	20°	85°	26	20

high electrode count. Conversely, passive devices typically rely on a wide and tapered shank to increase the space available for the metal interconnection lines to individual electrodes. [4], [30].

In this study, we also investigate the impact of insertion speed on insertion force. Based on our experimental evidence, we propose a novel closed-loop insertion method that relies on force measurements to detect the different implantation stages and to adapt insertion speed accordingly. To the best of our knowledge, the use of insertion force measurements for guiding and optimizing the implantation of tissue penetrating neural probes has never been reported in the literature.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Neural Probes

Insertion force measurements were performed using silicon neural probes with different geometrical features, as illustrated in Fig. 1(a) and summarized in Table I. Supplementary Fig. S1 displays a representative SEM image for each probe type.

Two different types of silicon devices were used:

- Devices produced at wafer level with a back side grinding process to reach a 50 μm thickness and a front side etching process to define probe geometry (example in Fig. 1(a)). This fabrication process poses some constraints on the minimum device thickness that can be achieved. Type A, B and D devices are CMOS-based probes
- Devices fabricated at die level in the IIT clean room facility (example in Fig. 1(b)). This fabrication process allows more freedom in the design of the cross-sectional dimensions (particularly the thickness) and tip geometries

Fig. 2. (a) Image of the insertion force measurement setup indicating the key components described in the “Insertion force measurement setup” paragraph. (b) Close-up image of the CAD model of the insertion force measurement setup. (c) Snapshot of the software tool developed for controlling the insertion and acquiring experimental data. The black panel allows to interface with the load cell, the blue panel with the linear actuator and the red panel with the PhysioSuite pulse oximeter.

of devices. Type C and E devices were realized with this approach.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging was used to measure the final probe dimensions and verify that they match the designed ones. To do so, probes were placed on a standard SEM stub using carbon-based conductive adhesive tape. The stub was then tilted at a 30° angle to measure probe thickness.

B. Insertion Force Measurement Setup

To perform in-vivo insertion force measurements we developed the custom experimental setup shown in Fig. 2(a). The key elements of the setup are a linear actuator (M-230.25, Physik Instrumente) for inserting the probe at the selected speed and a load cell (LSB200, Futek) for measuring insertion force during implantation in the brain (Fig. 2(b) shows a close-up of these elements). We selected the FSH03867 LSB200 load cell [31] because it has a low maximum load (10 g, 98.1 mN) and a nonrepeatability of 0.05%, allowing to reproducibly measure force changes in the order of $50 \mu\text{N}$. Custom 3D printed parts are used to mount the load cell co-axially on the linear actuator and to fix the assembly to a stereotactic arm. A support for the silicon probes was also 3D printed. This support includes an M3 screw for mechanical connection to the load cell, while the probe is attached to the opposite end using poly(2 ethyl 2 oxazoline), PEOX, a biocompatible water-soluble polymer.

A software tool, shown in Fig. 2(b), was developed with Matlab (version R2022b, Mathworks, USA) App designer to control the linear actuator to set the insertion speed and depth (blue panel in Fig. 2(b)), acquire insertion force data from the load cell (black panel in Fig. 2(b)) and physiological parameters from anesthetized animals (red panel in Fig. 2(b)). For the latter, we used the PhysioSuite pulse oximeter (Kent Scientific). Data of insertion experiments are stored as a .txt file for further analysis.

The integration of both the load cell and the linear actuator within the same software tool is crucial for implementing the closed-loop implantation procedure proposed in this work. Indeed, it allows to drive the movement of the actuator in real-time based on the feedback from the load cell.

C. In-Vivo Insertion Experiments

Insertion force measurements were performed on anesthetized Long Evan rats. This animal model was selected due to its relatively large brain, which allows to perform more insertions in each animal, thereby minimizing the required number of experimental subjects. Animals were anesthetized using isoflurane (4% isoflurane/ O_2 mix for induction and 1.5/2% for maintenance). Supplementary Fig. S2 A illustrates an example of an in-vivo experimental session. Four craniotomies were opened between the bregma and the lambda, symmetrically with respects to the midline of the skull, as schematized in Supplementary Fig. S2 B. The dura mater membrane was removed. Three/four implantations were performed in each craniotomy, avoiding superficial blood vessels. A new probe was used for each force measurement and insertion locations were spaced at least 1 mm apart from each other. To quantify the impact of probe size and tip geometry on dimpling dynamics, the different probes reported in Table I were inserted at a speed of $15 \mu\text{m/s}$. To quantify the impact of insertion speed on dimpling dynamics, Type D probes were implanted at the speeds of $2 \mu\text{m/s}$, $15 \mu\text{m/s}$ and $100 \mu\text{m/s}$. Dimpling distance and dimpling duration were defined respectively as the difference in force, actuator-imposed displacement, and time between the penetration event (black circle in Fig. 3(a)) and the beginning of probe/tissue contact (red circle in Fig. 3(a)). To determine significance, an ANOVA test with a Tukey-Kramer post hoc analysis using a 0.05 tolerance threshold was used. All procedures were performed in accordance with the European Directive 2010/63/EC and the Italian law for the protection of animals (license 666/2020PR, 21/07/2020).

D. Synchronization of Force With Implantation Video

An optical microscope (SZ61, Olympus-IMS) equipped with a camera (Moticam 3+, Motic) was used to observe and acquire videos of the insertion of silicon probes in the brain. Video recordings were then synchronized with force measurements to better understand and illustrate insertion dynamics. Synchronized implantation videos confirmed the reliability of

Fig. 3. (a) Insertion force over time for a Type A silicon probe. The red circle indicates contact with the brain, the black circle indicates dimpling force and the green circle indicates insertion end (b) Close-up on micro-forces due to respiration (black squares) and heartbeat (red circles).

force measurements for detecting the onset of probe-tissue contact and initial penetration within the brain parenchyma, as shown in Supplementary Video 1.

Custom Matlab scripts were used to create synchronized videos. Briefly, these scripts are used to refine synchronization between video and force measurement down to the temporal resolution of the camera (30 fps, around 33.3 ms temporal resolution). The insertion force signal was then resampled to match this frequency and plotted frame-by-frame on the video. Supplementary Video 1 illustrates an example of a synchronized video for the insertion of a Type A probe.

III. RESULTS

A. Insertion Force Measurements

Fig. 3(a) displays a representative insertion force measurement for a Type A probe inserted at a speed of $15 \mu\text{m/s}$. Force initially increases linearly as brain tissue is compressed elastically by the probe (dimpling stage). Once a critical force value is reached (black circle in Fig. 3(a)), the probe ruptures the brain surface and a drop in force value is detected. After this penetration event, insertion force remains very low in magnitude and nearly constant with implantation depth, despite the linear increase in probe-tissue contact area with depth. This indicates that in-vivo insertion force is not ruled by friction, consistently with what was reported in other studies [11]. The continuous micromotion of the brain due to heartbeat and respiration, which may prevent the onset of static friction, and/or the active pumping of cerebrospinal fluid, which may lubricate the probe-tissue

interface, are likely the cause of this friction-independent behavior.

Interestingly, two types of periodic small-magnitude peaks are clearly visible in the force measurement:

- Negative peaks with an amplitude ranging from 10 to $100 \mu\text{N}$ and a frequency of 1 Hz (black squares in Fig. 3(b))
- Positive peaks with a smaller amplitude (few μN) and a frequency of 5–6 Hz (red circles in Fig. 3(b))

These micro-forces are compatible with the amplitude and frequency of brain micromotion due to respiration (negative peaks) and heartbeat (positive peaks) [32]. A further analysis, reported in the following paragraph, demonstrates that these micro-forces are caused by physiological brain micromotion.

1) Analysis of Micromotion Forces: The PhysioSuite pulse oximeter (Kent Scientific) was used to carry out a concomitant and independent measurement of the animal respiration rate (RR) and heartbeat rate (HR) during in-vivo insertion force measurements. This method was used to verify if detected micro-forces are, as expected, related to these physiological phenomena.

To identify micro-forces, the force signal was high pass filtered (0.3 Hz frequency) to remove slow changes in force due to the insertion, as shown in Fig. 4(a). The Matlab “findpeaks” function was then used to identify negative (respiration) and positive (heartbeat) peaks. The RR and HR were estimated by taking the temporal lag between adjacent peaks and by converting it into beats per minute using (1) and (2) respectively.

$$RR = \frac{60}{T_{\text{resp}}} \quad (1)$$

$$HR = \frac{60}{T_{\text{heart}}} \quad (2)$$

where T_{resp} and T_{heart} are the duration of respiration and heartbeat intervals. A moving average was applied to the RR and HR signals to smoothen out variability. Fig. 4(b) and (c) show that the RR and HR estimated from force measurements closely match the values obtained using the PhysioSuite monitoring system, confirming that these micro-forces arise from respiration and heartbeat, respectively. This result confirms also the high sensitivity and reliability of our insertion force measuring setup.

2) Impact of Tip Geometry on Dimpling Force: We then performed insertion force measurements to investigate the impact of probe design on the dimpling stage of the implantation. The dimpling stage of probe insertion is crucial to determine the magnitude of induced iatrogenic injury, which drives subsequent FBR processes. During dimpling, the brain tissue is compressed, generating mechanical damage and lack of perfusion, particularly in shallow regions such as the cortex. This may induce ischemic damage and neuronal cell death. Moreover, the fast relaxation at the end of the dimpling stage induces a high shear stress at the probe-tissue interface, enhancing the probability of rupturing blood vessels. Additionally, our in-vivo insertion force measurements (and other evidence from the literature [11]) suggest that the dimpling force is typically the highest force value during implantation, while further insertion in the brain parenchyma can be accomplished with lower forces. These considerations motivated our choice of focusing on the dimpling

Fig. 4. Comparison of respiration rate and heartbeat rate estimated through the PhysioSuite pulse oximeter and from peaks in force measurements. (a) High-pass filtered force value (blue) with identified respiration (black squares) and heartbeat (red circles) peaks. (b) RR over time estimated from micro force peaks (red line) and from the PhysioSuite (blue line). (c) HR over time estimated from force measurement (red line) is very similar to that provided by the PhysioSuite (blue line).

dynamics. We assessed the impact of the following design features on dimpling force and distance:

- α tip angle: this angle indicates how sharp the probe is in the electrode plane. A sharper probe is expected to reduce dimpling magnitude
- β tip angle: this angle indicates how sharp the probe is in the plane perpendicular to the electrodes. For the devices used in this paper, this angle originates unintentionally from the fabrication process, and it is not a design feature.
- Probe width (W): a wider probe might induce a higher dimpling force compared to a thinner one by increasing the probe-brain contact area. However, sharp α angles are expected to mitigate this effect.
- Probe thickness (H): together with β , it determines the effective length of the edge compressing brain tissue during insertion. A thicker probe is therefore expected to increase dimpling force

Figs. 5(a) and (b) displays the influence of probe design on dimpling force and distance, respectively. Dimpling distance appears to be mainly influenced by the α tip angle. Statistically significant difference in dimpling distance was in fact only found between probes having different α tip angles (Type A and B vs. Type C, D and E), while differences in probe width and thickness did not result in significant changes. A similar observation is true for dimpling force, although the statistical significance analysis is not as conclusive. Type A and B probes display higher median dimpling forces compared to Type C, D and E. However, while the behavior of Type A is significantly different from Type C, D and E (as for dimpling distance), Type B probes differ only from Type E probes above the selected threshold of statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Overall, these results point towards the importance using a sharp probe for reducing dimpling force and distance. Supplementary Fig. S3 displays representative insertion force measurements for the different types of probes used in this study.

3) Impact of Insertion Speed on Dimpling Force: We investigated the impact of insertion speed on dimpling dynamics using Type D devices. This selection was made because these are the CMOS-based probes most commonly used in our lab and because their tip angle and dimensions result in low dimpling forces and distances, comparable to those of smaller devices (i.e., Type C and E). Three different insertion speeds, i.e. 2 $\mu\text{m/s}$,

Fig. 5. Impact of probe geometrical features on (a) dimpling force and (b) dimpling distance. All probes were inserted at a 15 $\mu\text{m/s}$ speed.

15 $\mu\text{m/s}$, and 100 $\mu\text{m/s}$, were tested. The rationale of selecting these speeds was to investigate a slow, intermediate and relatively fast insertion speed, according to the ranges provided by Fiath et al. [33].

Our insertion force measurements indicate that insertion speed does not play a decisive role on the magnitude of dimpling force and distance. The intermediate insertion speed of 15 $\mu\text{m/s}$ led to a lower median dimpling force (Fig. 6(a)) and dimpling distance (Fig. 6(b)) values. However, a statistically significant difference was only found between the dimpling force for insertion speeds of 2 $\mu\text{m/s}$ and 15 $\mu\text{m/s}$. Supplementary Fig. S4 displays representative insertion force measurements performed at the different speeds.

Fig. 6. (a) Dimpling force, (b) dimpling distance and (c) dimpling duration for the different insertion speeds. The experimentally measured duration of the dimpling stage closely matches the one predicted by (3).

Interestingly, although insertion speed does not largely influence dimpling dynamics, a slower insertion speed greatly increases the duration of the dimpling stage, as shown in Fig. 6(c). The dimpling distance is very similar for all insertion speeds. Therefore, the experimentally measured duration of the dimpling stage (T_{dimpling}) closely matches the one predicted using (3), as shown in Fig. 6(c).

$$T_{\text{dimpling}} = \frac{D_{\text{dimpling}}}{v_{\text{insertion}}} \quad (3)$$

Where D_{dimpling} is the median dimpling distance and $v_{\text{insertion}}$ is the insertion speed.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Insertion Force Measurements

We developed an insertion force measurement setup that allows to perform high resolution (μN range) insertion force measurements. Our in-vivo experiments highlight the importance of using sharp tip angles ($\alpha = 20$ degrees) for limiting the extent of tissue dimpling, which is crucial for minimizing acute tissue damage. On the other hand, device cross-sectional dimensions (W and H) do not play a crucial role on dimpling dynamics. W was not expected to largely affect the dimpling stage for the relatively sharp devices (small α) used in this work. Indeed, the area of probe tip in contact with brain tissue is expected to mainly depend on the α angle rather than on W. However, we surprisingly assess that also H has a negligible impact on dimpling dynamics. Indeed, Type D devices, which are much thicker than Type C and E but have the same α angle result in comparable dimpling forces and distances. The β tip angle, although it is relatively large for these devices, might explain this observation. This angle decreases the effective length of the tip edge in contact with the brain (making it lower than H). Solutions to sharpen the β angle have been proposed in the literature [22], but they are typically not suitable to scale up the fabrication of devices.

Gen Li et al. [34] recently published interesting results on the impact of probe cross-sectional dimension and tip sharpness on insertion dynamics in an Agar gel tissue phantom. Differently from what we observed in-vivo, the authors reported that device thickness significantly affects dimpling dynamics by altering the cracking modality of the tissue phantom. Moreover, probe

tip angle (α) does not influence the dimpling stage in this experimental setting if the angle is lower than 45° . These discrepancies with our in-vivo findings seem to indicate that the Agar gel tissue phantom does not accurately model the cracking modalities and insertion dynamics occurring in-vivo, consistently with what was previously reported from Obaid et al. [11]. However, the innovative approach of investigating cracking modalities while measuring insertion force is extremely interesting, although not directly applicable to in-vivo experiments.

We also investigated the impact of implantation speed on insertion dynamics. At the slowest speed, we expected tissue penetration to occur at lower force values, because the tip is in contact with the tissue for more time, thus applying a longer lasting local stress. However, it appears that a critical force (local pressure) value must be reached to penetrate brain tissue, while a lower force applied for a longer time is not sufficient. This result is consistent with other evidence collected under similar experimental conditions [11], [17]. A slower speed, however, does significantly increase dimpling duration. This is expected to negatively affect brain tissue by generating more extensive mechanical stress and by hindering perfusion, potentially inducing ischemic damage. Therefore, based on the dimpling stage alone, a faster insertion appears to be beneficial because it reduces dimpling duration, without increasing the dimpling force and distance. However, Fiath et al. [33] reported that a slower insertion speed results in higher quality acute electrophysiological signals. This observation, which we also independently made in our own electrophysiology experiments, potentially indicates that slow speeds are more appropriate after the end of the dimpling stage. The consideration that a custom speed should be used in the different insertion stages and the requirement of improving the safety and reliability of implantation prompted us to devise a novel closed-loop insertion procedure guided by force measurements. A potential implementation of this procedure is detailed in the following paragraph.

B. Closed-Loop Implantation Protocol

Insertion force measurements allow to implement an optimized closed-loop controlled implantation procedure (schematized in Fig. 7(a)), which can be divided into three major steps:

- placing the probe in contact with the brain
- the dimpling stage

Fig. 7. (a) Overview of closed-loop implantation procedure. The probe is moved towards the brain until contact detection (magenta dot). Now the insertion protocol may start (blue square). Initially, a relatively high speed (e.g., $20 \mu\text{m/s}$) is used to reduce the duration of the dimpling stage. After initial tissue penetration (red diamond) a slower insertion (e.g., $2 \mu\text{m/s}$) should be used to improve the quality of acute electrophysiological recordings (green triangle) (b) Control signal for contact detection. Force signal is differentiated sample-by-sample to highlight micromotion forces. (c) Control signal for dimpling detection. The force signal is sub-sampled at 1s intervals before differentiating it, to remove the contribution of micromotion forces. (d) Example of probe buckling. The inflection in the force-displacement signal (red circle) indicates the onset of buckling. Further increases in force cause the probe to break (black circle) (e) Contact detection algorithm. Force signal is initially differentiated sample-by-sample. After acquiring a defined number of samples (N_{cal}), a threshold value (Thr) is calculated by multiplying the standard deviation of the differentiated force (F_{diff}) by a coefficient ($Coeff$). New samples of F_{diff} are compared to this threshold value. If F_{diff} is higher than the threshold and another event occurred within the previous 1.5 seconds, contact is confirmed. (f) Dimpling detection algorithm. Force signal is sub-sampled at 1 s intervals to remove the contribution of micromotion forces. This sub-sampled signal is then differentiated and a threshold value (Thr) is calculated by multiplying the standard deviation of the differentiated force (F_{diff}) by a coefficient ($Coeff$). A moving average operator is applied to F_{diff} to reduce variability. If the absolute value of this signal (F_{Av}) is larger than the threshold, dimpling is detected.

- insertion in brain parenchyma to the target region

The first step, although apparently trivial, is not easy to accomplish consistently without force feedback. On the other hand, high sensitivity insertion force measurements allow to rapidly and reliably detect probe-tissue contact, as described in the following paragraph (Section IV-B1). To reach the brain in a relatively short time, and to avoid excessive displacement during the time required for contact detection (typically few seconds), we propose a speed of $15\text{--}20 \mu\text{m/s}$ in this stage.

Once the probe is in contact with the brain, the actual implantation may start. Insertion speed does not significantly alter dimpling dynamics but it greatly affects dimpling duration. Our aim in this stage is therefore to reduce dimpling duration while simultaneously avoiding excessively high speeds. Dimpling distance is the product of insertion speed and dimpling duration and our evidence shows that dimpling distance is constant with speed. The problem of minimizing the combined value of dimpling duration and insertion speed can therefore be resembled to that of minimizing the perimeter of a rectangle with a given area. The minimum perimeter is achieved when the two edges of the rectangle have the same value. In our specific case, the dimpling distance is around $400 \mu\text{m}$, therefore the lowest combined value is achieved using an insertion speed of $20 \mu\text{m/s}$ and a dimpling duration of 20 s. We therefore propose to use this speed during the dimpling stage. While this value is only indicative and a

range of similar speeds are expected to yield comparable results, it is important to note that ischemia as short as 2.5 minutes has been shown to result in acute and sustained brain damage [35], [36]. This evidence suggests that a slow insertion, leading to a dimpling duration longer than 150 s, may cause ischemic damage and should therefore be avoided.

The end of the dimpling stage can be detected from force measurements, as described in paragraph Section IV-B2. Once the end of the dimpling stage is detected, a pause in the insertion procedure is implemented. This pause allows the complete relaxation of brain tissue around the probe, before proceeding to deeper brain regions. Once the pause is completed, a slower insertion speed can be used ($1\text{--}2 \mu\text{m/s}$).

A relatively fast speed during the dimpling stage minimizes the duration of brain compression and consequent ischemia, while a slow insertion after initial penetration allows brain tissue to comply with the probe and yields improved electrophysiological recordings. This procedure is expected to improve the quality of acute electrophysiological recordings and to minimize iatrogenic injury, reducing FBR and thus improving chronic electrical interfacing performances.

The continuous monitoring of insertion force during implantation also enables to detect abnormal events and halt the implantation procedure. For example, a large increase in force could indicate misalignment between the probe axis and the insertion

axis, which should be corrected. Indeed, this misalignment induces greater implantation forces and more extensive tissue damage. Additionally, insertion force measurements allow to detect (and prevent) probe buckling and consequent mechanical failure in real-time, as discussed in paragraph Section IV-B3.

A different closed-loop approach using pressure measurements to increase recording stability and to avoid disturbance of local perfusion was previously proposed by Angotzi et al. [37]. However, this system is not suitable to perform the implantation procedure proposed in this work, because it does not measure axial insertion force but rather the pressure exerted by the headstage on the surface of the brain.

1) Contact Detection Algorithm: The detection of micro-motion forces allows to precisely and rapidly detect contact between the probe and brain tissue. At the typical insertion speed used for probe implantation ($\mu\text{m/s}$ to hundreds of $\mu\text{m/s}$ range), this strategy is faster and more reliable than detecting the slow increase in force due to brain dimpling.

To detect contact, force signal is differentiated sample-by-sample by subtracting the $(i-1)^{\text{th}}$ sample from the i^{th} sample. Fig. 7(b) shows an example of this differentiated signal. A threshold value is calculated as the standard deviation of the differentiated force signal (over a calibration period) multiplied by a coefficient selected based on previous force measurements. To decrease the number of false-positives, contact is confirmed only if two above threshold events are detected within a certain time interval. This interval was set to 1.5 seconds based on typical values of RR, since respiration micro-forces are mainly responsible for contact detection. This choice significantly improved the specificity of the algorithm, which is schematized in Fig. 7(e).

High-sensitivity insertion force measurements are essential for this algorithm, which allows to reliably set the starting point of the implantation procedure.

2) Dimpling Detection Algorithm: The sudden drop in force value when the probe penetrates brain tissue can be used to detect the end of dimpling. Force signal is initially sub-sampled at one second intervals to remove the contribution of micromotion forces and subsequently differentiated as previously detailed for contact detection. Fig. 7(c) illustrates an example of the control signal used for dimpling detection. A threshold value is calculated as the standard deviation of the sub-sampled force signal before contact detection multiplied by a coefficient selected based on previous force measurements. A moving average operator with a window of three samples is applied to the signal before checking for threshold crossing. This reduces variability and decreases the rate of false-positives. The dimpling detection algorithm is schematized in Fig. 7(f).

The detection of dimpling end is key for the implementation of a closed-loop implantation control algorithm. Indeed, it enables the use a faster speed during the compression stage and a slower speed during further insertion into the brain parenchyma. Moreover, the introduction of a pause in the insertion protocol at the end of the dimpling stage allows for complete tissue relaxation, potentially reducing neurovascular and cortical damage.

3) Buckling Detection: Buckling is a phenomenon which occurs when the probe (or in general a mechanical structure)

is subjected to a critical axial load ($F_{buckling}$). Small increases above this critical value result in device bending and, eventually, in mechanical failure. $F_{buckling}$ can be estimated using (4).

$$F_{buckling} = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{(kL)^2} \quad (4)$$

Where E is the Young's modulus of the probe substrate, I is the area moment of inertia of the shank cross-section, k is the effective shank length (based on boundary conditions) and L is the physical shank length.

Buckling precludes the successful implantation of tissue penetrating neural probes and it should be avoided to prevent unnecessary tissue damage and device breakage. Insertion force measurements allow to identify buckling by measuring changes in the rate at which force increases. When the probe buckles, an inflection point can be seen in the force-displacement graph (red circle in Fig. 7(d)). This feature can be detected based on the value of the second derivative of the signal, which becomes negative. We developed an algorithm for the real-time detection of buckling which allows to halt the insertion procedure before breaking the probe (black circle in Fig. 7(d)). Supplementary Video 2 illustrates an example of buckling detection/prevention when pushing a probe at a $15 \mu\text{m/s}$ speed against a rigid substrate. The real-time detection/prevention of buckling is crucial for improving the safety of the implantation procedure and to decrease the risk of breaking the probe. This increased safety is beneficial for any in-vivo or BMI experiment.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we investigated the impact of probe cross-sectional dimensions, tip sharpness and implantation speed on insertion force, which was used as a metric to assess the impact of these parameters to the device invasiveness. The aim of this characterization is to advance the design and implantation procedure tailored to the new geometries and performances of high-density CMOS-based neural devices to minimize their invasiveness and optimize their electrical interfacing performances both in acute and chronic settings.

We found that the α tip angle has a dominant impact during the dimpling stage and that sharp probes ($\alpha = 20^\circ$) induce lower tissue compression irrespective of their cross-sectional dimensions. Sharpening the probe by reducing the β angle is also expected to reduce tissue dimpling. However, no solution to reliably control this angle through large-scale microfabrication processes is currently available.

Insertion speed does not significantly affect dimpling dynamics but slower speeds drastically increase dimpling duration, potentially exacerbating invasiveness. Despite this, slow insertion speeds are reported to improve the quality of acute electrophysiological recordings. These considerations led us to devise an implantation procedure relying on force measurements to identify and set the optimal speed in the different insertion stages. This closed-loop approach also enhances safety by avoiding excessively high insertion forces and by preventing probe buckling/breaking.

The use of sharp devices, implanted with the proposed insertion method, can reduce the invasiveness of stiff tissue penetrating neural probes and improve the reliability and yield of electrophysiology experiments. Further, continuous monitoring of insertion force and real-time algorithms for the detection of abnormal events can be used to improve the safety of the implantation procedure. Such advancements are crucial for exploiting the unprecedented spatiotemporal resolution of CMOS-based neural probes in preclinical research, and to develop experimental studies in clinical setting.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors greatly thank Corticale S.r.l., Genova, Italy for providing SiNAPS probes for insertion force measurements. The Open University Affiliated Research Centre at Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (ARC@IIT) is part of the Open University, Milton Keynes MK7 6AA, United Kingdom.

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